

Entrepreneurial Skills of Student Entrepreneurs

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ABSTRACT: Entrepreneurial skills play an essential role in the entrepreneurial process to business success, especially for student entrepreneurs. This paper aims to identify the level of importance of entrepreneurial skills of student entrepreneurs at the Mindanao State University Tawi-Tawi College of Technology and Oceanography. A descriptive research method was used. The snowball and convenience sampling technique were applied for respondents' identification. There were 55 students who participated in this study from different course programs. A Likert-scaling survey questionnaire was employed for data collection. The percentage method was utilized to analyse the data collected. The result shows that all entrepreneurial skills are vitally important to the respondents. Creativity is the highest value as very important. However, communication and leadership skills are the highest response on not important. The significance is to help student entrepreneurs for business continuity through the technical assistance of the university by conducting seminars and training and financial support by public and private organizations.

KEYWORDS: Entrepreneurial Characteristics, Entrepreneurial Skills, Entrepreneurship, Student Entrepreneurs, Youth Entrepreneurship

I. INTRODUCTION

Entrepreneurship provides a solution to the problem of economy (Adejimola & Olufunmilayo, 2009), gender bias (Starchenko, 2020), fresh graduates' unemployment (Yohana, 2020), collective adjustment (Yusof et al., 2007), social unemployment (Setiawan, 2014; Chen et al., 2018; Li, 2021) especially in youth sector (Gwija et al, 2014; Farid & Rahman, 2020), and students' expenses (Caliat, 2024). For students, entrepreneurship creates a significant impact on their lives. It encourage-ages them to do business after college (Kurdyś-Kujawska & Wojtkowska, 2023; Caliat et al., 2024). According to Rembiasz (2017), students are motivated to engage in business and identify obstacles to their entrepreneurial engagement.

According to Yun & McNaughton (2021), at the University of Auckland, 8.4% of students were active young and small entrepreneurs, whereas almost 50% had no partners. About 45% of them are prepared to launch other businesses and man-age their current business separately. 28.2% were focused on their existing business. With managing the new and existing businesses, the entrepreneurs shall understand how to administer and handle using their education, training and skills. Indeed, there is no formula required for a successful entrepreneur.

However, it is the skills that define success (Chapter 3 Entrepreneurs: Key Characteristics and Skills, n.d.). Various small-medium enterprises experienced failure due to the failure to identify their strengths and weaknesses (Lowden, 2007). Hence, knowledge is not only essential for a student entrepreneur (Schimperna et al., 2022) but also for various skills with an interdisciplinary approach to business (Haynie & Shepherd, 2009). Furthermore, the most valuable skills of successful entrepreneurs must be identified and measured (Sandoval, 2022). According to Romero and Gono (2021), entrepreneurial knowledge and skills are the primary obstacles that hinder students from pursuing business. Skills shall be identified and assessed by the entrepreneurs so they can understand mentally how to manage the financial, human and technical resources.

Thus, this study is rooted in the importance of entrepreneurial skills for success. It identifies the level of importance of various entrepreneurial skills. This study imparts information for student entrepreneurs who should understand the basic skills and their level of importance to success.

Entrepreneurial Skills of Student Entrepreneurs

A. Entrepreneurship

Entrepreneurship is a discipline that has various subfields according to its uses in society (Ratten, 2023). It is a complex system (Oganisjana & Koke, 2012) in the organization where new products are created from the inception of ideas to business engagement (Sousa & Almeida, 2014). Creating a product is not only done by an organization. However, it could also be made by individuals who engage (Stanford University, n.d.) to satisfy consumer demand (Kollie et al., 2011).

It is more than business startups; it includes the synergy of personal development skills and competencies (Cooney, 2012). An individual must undergo a process to create a business enterprise. Developing a business includes preparing pertinent business documents, assessing the characters and skills of entrepreneurs, and assessing the external environment. If students are able, they can enter or establish a new market.

B. Entrepreneurial Skills

It is fulfilling to pursue business career out-comes psychologically and economically (Ziemianski & Golik, 2020). An entrepreneur's career requires various skills to adapt to a changing business environment (Yener, 2020). However, entrepreneurial skills are part of psychological outcomes that are anchored to a universal concept according to the field of psychology. Chell (2013) defined skills as a complex concept that comprises cognitive, affective, behavioral, and context.

Entrepreneurial skills equate to business skills, which help an individual function in a changing business environment. They are a set needed to create innovative products that generate solutions in the community (Lyons, 2002). Creating innovative products requires attitudes and skills to begin (Vicens et al., 2022). Moreover, business skills are essential to business success (Irene, 2017). These skills are required to manage an enterprise successfully (Zahra et al., 2014), including decision making, risk taking, communication, creativity, ability to prepare business plan/research, negotiation, sales technique, financial knowledge, social networking, leadership, critical thinking and time management.

Decision-making is part of every aspect of human life, where individuals use their mental capacity to react to a situation (Colakkadioglu & Celik, 2016). It comprises three components: envision the objective, identify significant substitutes, and compare identified substitutes using assessment method (Siebert et al., 2022). According to Dodgson and Gann (2020), students should understand how to make decisions in solving problems. Through attending business training, student entrepreneurs acquire ideas for making decisions and the willingness to take risks (Kusmintarti et al., 2016) in addressing solutions to business problems (Littunen, 2000). The vital systematic decision of entrepreneurs lies in the future of the business. In an organization, the company head is responsible for making decisions using analysis and critical thinking (Ding, 2022; de Vries & Kroukamp, 2022).

Risk-taking is a prerequisite for achieving progress (Komulainen et al., 2009). It is an assurance of an individual's possible loss in a fortuitous event (Trimpop, 1994). Individuals make an assurance about dealing with uncertainties with a natural reaction to protect their identity (Zinn, 2016). In the business context, entrepreneurs must possess risk-taking skills in new ventures (Kerr et al., 2017; Fuentelsaz et al., 2018). According to Cater et al. (2022), risk-taking positively impacts entrepreneurs' entrepreneurial intentions. Aspiring business leaders were more motivated to take risks (Macko & Tyzka, 2009). Moreover, student entrepreneurs have a higher risk-taking inclination (Anwar & Saleem, 2019).

Communication involved exchanging ideas, beliefs, impressions, and even information (Sen, 2009). Entrepreneurs and business heads agreed on the importance of communication ability (Conrad & Newberry, 2011). In business, one of the components of entrepreneurial competencies is effective communication, which helps entrepreneurs explain, discuss, sell, and promote their products in the market (CEFE, n.d.). Effective communication helps entrepreneurs to convince investors (Dodgson & Gann, 2020) and strong will to entrepreneurial success (Makhbul, 2011). However, a lack of communication skills impacts entrepreneurs' failure (Bhaskar et al., 2022). Therefore, communication skills are essential for entrepreneurs.

Creativity is defined as a mental manner and principal competency that brings out and produces the discovery of new ideas through imagination (Dampérat et al., 2016; Tang et al., 2018). Creative ideas start from a dream, an insight, or mere observation (Habaradas & Tullao, 2017). In addition, the entrepreneurial process is linked with creative process activities to establish entrepreneurial applications (Kruger, 2005). Hence, it is essential for the entrepreneur (Birdthistle, 2008) and valid for new product and systems development using their talent and vision in business operation, also called creative entrepreneurship (Bujor & Avasilcai, 2016).

According to Cater et al. (2022), creativity is positively significant with entrepreneurial intentions and highly affects the EI in creating new and managing businesses (Koe et al., 2018 & Rakib et al., 2022). For student entrepreneurs, creativity impacts the team (Gundry et al., 2014) and improves current business methods (bin Mazla et al., 2020).

Acquiring skills is essential for business students in business education and employment (Calma, 2023). Skills such as preparing and developing a plan are primary skills for entrepreneurs to achieve specific goals in various business functions (CEFE, n.d.). A plan must be written, such as a business plan and research. To develop a good business plan, according to Bapanova et al. (2023),

Entrepreneurial Skills of Student Entrepreneurs

one of the various skills identified was research analysis and evaluation. Schrum and Bogdewiecz (2021) suggested that students must develop essential re-search skills. Enhancing this skill through competition helps participants produce startups and develop entrepreneurial skills (Russell et al., 2008).

Negotiation is defined as a manner of communication among individuals that has a common pursuit (Pienaar & Spoelstra, 1999), which has three views, including “process, the respective parties' objectives, and bargaining” (Ashcroft, 2004). It is also equated with persuasion or influence management (Lehmann & Winer, 2005). It is a crucial to success in the business working conditions (Fioravanti et al., 2022) and smooth transactions between suppliers and customers (Deac et al., 2014). The study by Petříková & Soroková (2016), one of the top responses of the student is the ability to persuade.

The study by Powers et al. (2014) discusses three conceptual dimensions of sales management skills – interpersonal, technical, and strategic skills. These three dimensions were essential to the success of sales management (Razmak et al., 2023). According to the study by Alvarez et al. (2015), there was an increasing demand for online sales training, so employers required more various sales skill sets and offered continuous training (Høgevoid et al., 2021).

Financial knowledge is a subset of financial literacy that should be used effectively for financial resources management of financial well-being (Hung et al., 2009). Guliman (2015) found out that most business owners have low levels of financial knowledge. The study by Dwi Radianto et al. (2019) found that young entrepreneurial financial literacy levels were moderate. Finally, it helps entrepreneurs decide on savings and financial management of their business (Cossa et al., 2018).

Networking is a process of strengthening the social relationships inside and outside an organization (Gibson et al., 2014), especially with customers and clients (CEFE, n.d.). According to Chen et al. (2010), student entrepreneurs have a high level of social networking skills, which helps to develop entrepreneurial intention (Zafar et al., 2012; Twum et al., 2021) and creates new business engagement (Lindelöf & Löfsten, 2004). A social-character person finds it easy to establish and maintain social relationships that might be in-vested the new business ideas by its network (Kusmintarti et al., 2016).

Leadership is the ability to create a vision for the firm and inspire the employees to achieve its goal collectively (CEFE, n.d.). It encompasses attitudes and behaviors influencing followers (Moore & Rudd, 2004). It is one of the essential skills to achieve business success and avail of business opportunities (Jasra et al., 2011). However, students develop leadership competencies through program-related roles such as organizing entrepreneurial leadership (Bagheri & Lope Pihie, 2012). Characteristics of a student entrepreneur leader are love challenges, adaptability (Bagheri et al., 2013), ability to decide quickly in difficult situations (Abu Mostafa et al., 2021), and vision-oriented (Omeihe et al., 2023).

Critical-thinking skills are defined as the systematic and rational method of providing an answer to a question. It is a systematic way of responding to the inquiry and explaining how a company can survive (Habaradas & Tullao, 2017). Tem et al. (2020) discovered that critical thinking is one of the most essential soft skills to expand entrepreneurs' competitiveness and productivity. Entrepreneurs must understand quantitative analysis, interpretation, and general number crunching (Lehmann & Winer, 2005). A study by Rodriguez and Lieber (2020) shows the positive significance of an entrepreneurial mind-set, especially in critical thinking and problem-solving. In addition, there is evidence that critical thinking has a positive correlation with creativity (Eggers et al., 2017) and a significant effect on entrepreneurship levels (Kırbaşlar & Özsoy-Güneş, 2015).

Time management aims to use time effectively while doing certain activities (Effeney et al., 2013) to accomplish goal-directed activities within a span of time (Little, 2018). It is an individuals' want to achieve greater independence (Davies et al., 2002) and a basic ability for life success (Gül et al., 2024). All aspects of life relate to time management, whether in individual or business organizations (Sayari et al., 2017). It is considered necessary for entrepreneurs to know how to handle pressures in busy lifestyles and take care of the business efficiently (CEFE, n.d.).

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The descriptive design is used to collect information from the primary participants. The critical respondents of this survey are the 55 student entrepreneurs from various colleges at the MSUTCTO. More information on the list of student entrepreneurs from any office on campus needs to be provided. Therefore, this study utilizes snowball and convenience sampling techniques. The assistance of the participants is essential to assist the research in identifying other potential respondents.

The survey method is employed to gather relevant information from the respondents through a structured questionnaire. The questionnaire is composed of two pages with three parts, including a personal profile, a business profile, and a rating on the important skills of an entrepreneur. There were questions that needed to be answered through a checklist. Moreover, the primary data were analysed using percentage analysis. The information is presented on tables.

Entrepreneurial Skills of Student Entrepreneurs

III. RESULTS & DISCUSSION

A. Personal and Business Profile of the Respondents

61% of the respondents were female, 36% were male, and 4% were members of the LGBTQ community. 23.36 years old was the average age of the key respondents. 34% of the respondents had mothers who were full-time housewives, and their fathers were government employees.

The business entity is managed depending on the form of ownership. Forms include sole proprietorship, partnerships, and corporations. 56% of the student entrepreneurs supervised the business by individual. Partnership (44%) administered the business. In this study, no corporation was formed by the students.

Moreover, entrepreneurs invest in services, merchandising, and manufacturing. 54% of the respondents were engaged in trading, while 41% were in manufacturing. Only 5% were ventured with services.

In merchandising, the student entrepreneurs in-vested in buying and selling goods, with 32% selling foods. Only 28% ventured into jewellery or clothing, and 16% into perfume. Those who manufactured were selling food. The 5% engaged in service work, including photography and transportation.

It is essential to identify the sources of capital in business. The student entrepreneurs sourced their investment from their allowance (54%), family (31%), and risk capital (11%). Moreover, the respondents (35%) gained estimated sales with a range of PhP 1,000.00—PhP999.00. 27% managed to collect PhP 16,000.00 and above.

B. Entrepreneurial Skills

Skills are prerequisites in managing a business, and the entrepreneur must understand the dynamics of using them to achieve the entrepreneurial firm's goals. The respondents rated these skills (Table 1) based on their importance: decision-making, risk-taking, communication, creativity, ability to prepare research or business plan, negotiation, sales technique, financial knowledge, networking, leadership, critical thinking, and time management.

The result shows that 61.82% of the respondents agreed that decision-making skills are vital. At the same time, 21.82% agreed to the essential. Decision-making is important for direction and strategic planning (Shepherd & Patzelt, 2017). Moreover, 72.73% of the respondents had varying positive degrees about the importance of risk-taking. This skill positively influences the decision for entrepreneurial intention (Vodă et al., 2019). Meanwhile, communication skills are vitally important to 60% of student entrepreneurs. 25.45% agreed that it is essential in business. Soft skills like communication are vital for entrepreneurs to labor market competence (Tem et al., 2020).

Table 1. Respondents' percentage on importance of skills of entrepreneurs

Skills	Very Important	Important	Neutral	Not Important	Very unimportant
Decision Making	61.82	21.82	14.55	0.00	0.00
Risk Taking	52.73	20.00	20.00	5.45	0.00
Communication	60.00	25.45	3.64	7.27	1.82
Creativity	63.64	20.00	10.91	3.64	0.00
Ability to Prepare Business Plan/Research	49.09	36.36	9.09	1.82	1.82
Negotiation	56.36	21.82	12.73	5.45	0.00
Sales Technique	54.55	29.09	10.91	3.64	0.00
Knowledge on finance	54.55	27.27	14.55	1.82	0.00
Networking	41.82	32.73	18.18	1.82	1.82
Leadership	54.55	18.18	14.55	7.27	1.82
Critical thinking or rational thinking	49.09	30.91	12.73	5.45	0.00
Time Management	61.82	25.45	5.45	5.45	0.00

IV. CONCLUSIONS

Based on the data discussed it answers the importance on the various skills in business ventures. According to Li et al. (2023), entrepreneurial skills are essential to entrepreneurial success. In the study, all skills are essential in business ventures to increase

Entrepreneurial Skills of Student Entrepreneurs

sales, expand their market horizon, and protect their market share. However, some skills have a value given by the respondent to be 50% below on a very important scale, including the ability to prepare a business plan/research, networking skills, and critical thinking. Moreover, among the enumerated entrepreneurial skills, the ability to prepare a business plan has almost the same value with very important and important scales.

It is crucial to manage a business without giving importance to various entrepreneurial skills (Bagheri & Lope Pihie, 2011). There are skills that are given a value of above 5% in not important, including risk-taking, communication, negotiation, leadership, critical thinking, and time management. But this 5% can never affect the importance level of the result. In conclusion, all skills have positive varying responses.

This study provides ideas for the campus to plan various activities to help the student entrepreneurs continue their business ventures and reach entrepreneurial goals. It informs concerned agencies to provide financial and technical support and expand their market. In addition, this study is essential for the participants to identify what skills they want to improve and develop.

REFERENCES

- 1) Abu Mostafa, Y.A., Salama, A.A., Abu Amuna, Y.M. and Aqel, A.M. 2021 The Role of Strategic Leadership in Activating Time Management Strategies to Enhance Administrative Creativity Skills "Case Study: Al-Azhar University." *International Journal of Academic Management Science Research*, Vol. 5 (3), pp 36-48. ISSN: 2643-900X
- 2) Adejimiola, A.S., and Olunfunmilayo, T-O. 2009 Spinning off an Entrepreneurship Culture among Nigerian University Students: Prospects and Challenges. *African Journal of Business Management*, Vol.3 (3), 080–088. ISSN 1993-8233
- 3) Alvarez, C. M. O., Taylor, K. A. and Rauseo, N. A. 2015 Creating Thoughtful Salespeople: Experiential Learning to Improve Critical Thinking Skills in Traditional and Online Sales Education. *Marketing Education Review*, 25(3), 233–243. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10528008.2015.1044859>
- 4) Anwar, I. and Saleem, I. 2019 Exploring Entrepreneurial Characteristics among University Students: An Evidence from India. *Asia Pacific Journal of Innovation and Entrepreneurship*, Vol. 13 No. 3, pp. 282–295. DOI 10.1108/APJIE-07-2018-0044
- 5) Ashcroft, S. 2004 Commercial Negotiation Skills. *Industrial and Commercial Training*, Vol. 36 No. 6, pp. 229–233. <https://doi.org/10.1108/00197850410556658>
- 6) Bagheri, A. and Lope Pihie, Z.A. 2011 On Becoming an Entrepreneurial Leader: A Focus on the Impacts of University Entrepreneurship Programs. *American Journal of Applied Sciences*, 8 (9): 884-892. ISSN 1546-9239
- 7) Bagheri, A. and Lope Pihie, Z. A. 2012 Role of University Entrepreneurship Programs in Developing Students' Entrepreneurial Leadership Competencies: Perspectives from Malaysian Undergraduate Students. *Journal of Education for Business*, 88(1), 51–61. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08832323.2011.638681>
- 8) Bagheri, A., Lope Pihie, Z. A. and Krauss, S. E. 2013 Entrepreneurial leadership competencies among Malaysian university student entrepreneurial leaders. *Asia Pacific Journal of Education*, 33(4), 493–508. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02188791.2013.822789>
- 9) Bapanova, G. K., Orekhova, N. V., Kadirsizova, S. B., Kasbayeva, G. S. and Sholpankulova, G. K. 2023 Research Skills as the Student Learning Achievement. *International Journal of Educational Reform*, 0(0). <https://doi.org/10.1177/10567879231155874>
- 10) Bhaskar, P., K, G. and V, V. 2022 A Study on Challenges Faced by Entrepreneurs. *Journal of Positive School Psychology*, Vol. 6, No. 10, 3871-3879.
- 11) Bin Mazla, M.I., Bin Jabor, M.K., Tufail, K., Yakin, A.F.N. and Zainal, H. 2020 The Roles of Creativity and Innovation in Entrepreneurship. *Advances in Social Science, Education and Humanities Research*, <https://doi.org/10.2991/assehr.k.200921.035>
- 12) Birdthistle, N. 2008 An examination of tertiary students' desire to found an enterprise. *Education + Training*. 50(7), 552-567. DOI: 10.1108/00400910810909027
- 13) Bujor, A. and Avasilcai, S. 2016 The Creative Entrepreneur: A Framework of Analysis. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 221, 21 – 28. doi: 10.1016/j.sbspro.2016.05.086
- 14) Caliat, C. (2024). Entrepreneurial Intention and Influence for Entrepreneurial Engagement of Student Entrepreneurs. (2024). *Social Science and Humanities Journal (SSHJ)*, 8(04), 34983-34999
- 15) Caliat, C.J., Dalhadi, N.J. and Ishmael, K.M. 2024 Entrepreneurship Education in the Lens of the Senior High School Students. *ASEAN Journal on Science and Technology for Development*, Vol. 41 (1), Art 2. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.61931/2224-9028.1554>
- 16) Calma, A. 2023 Using Assurance of Learning Data to Assess Business Students' Research Skills. *Quality Assurance in Education*, Vol. 31 No. 4, pp. 586-599. <https://doi.org/10.1108/QAE-01-2023-0003>

Entrepreneurial Skills of Student Entrepreneurs

- 17) Cater, J.J., Young, M., Al-Shammari, M. and James, K. 2022 Re-Exploring Entrepreneurial Intentions and Personality Attributes during a Pandemic. *Journal of International Education in Business*, Vol. 15 No. 2, pp. 311–330. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JIEB-04-2021-0050>
- 18) Chapter 3 Entrepreneurs: Key Characteristics and Skills. n.d. Center for Economic & Financial Education (CEFE). http://www.cefe.illinois.edu/tools/making%20a%20job/maj_student%20guide%20sample.pdf
- 19) Chell, E. 2013 Review of Skill and the Entrepreneurial Process. *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behaviour and Research*, 19(1): 6-31. <https://doi.org/10.1108/13552551311299233>
- 20) Chen, S-C., Hsiao, H-C., Chang, J-C., Chou, C-M and Chen, D.-C. 2018 Strengthen Entrepreneurial Capacity in Entrepreneurial Competitions—International Conference on Cognition and Exploratory Learning in Digital Age. ISBN: 978-989-8533-81-4
- 21) Chen, W., Weng, C.S. and Hsu, H. 2010 A study of the Entrepreneurship of Taiwanese Youth by the Chinese Entrepreneur Aptitude Scale. *Journal of Technology Management in China*, 5(1) p.26-39. DOI: 10.1108/17468771011032778
- 22) Colakkadioglu, O. and Celik, B. 2016 The Effect of Decision-Making Skill Training Programs on Self-Esteem and Decision-Making Styles. *Eurasian Journal of Educational Research*, 65, 259-276. <http://dx.doi.org/10.14689/ejer.2016.65.15>
- 23) Conrad, D. and Newberry, R. 2011 24 Business Communication Skills: Attitudes of Human Resource Managers versus Business Educators. *American Communication Journal*, Vol 13 (1).
- 24) Cooney, T. 2012 Entrepreneurship Skills for Growth-Orientated Businesses. Danish Business Authority. Retrieved on May 2024 from https://www.oecd.org/cfe/leed/cooney_entrepreneurship_skills_HGF.pdf
- 25) Cossa, A., Madaleno, M. and Mota, J. 2018 Financial Literacy Importance for Entrepreneurship: A Literature Survey. *European Conference on Innovation and Entrepreneurship*, pp. 909-9016. <https://doi.org/https://tinyurl.com/ECIE18>
- 26) Dampérat, M, Jeannot, F., Jongmans, E. and Jolibert, A. 2016 Team Creativity: Creative Self-Efficacy, Creative Collective Efficacy and Their Determinants. *Recherche et Applications en Marketing*, 31(3): 6–25. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2051570716650164>
- 27) Davies, D.K., Stock, S.E. and Wehmeyer, M.L. 2002 Enhancing Independent Time-Management Skills of Individuals with Mental Retardation Using a Palmtop Personal Computer. *Ment Retard*, 40 (5): 358–365. [https://doi.org/10.1352/0047-6765\(2002\)040%3C0358:EITMSO%3E2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1352/0047-6765(2002)040%3C0358:EITMSO%3E2.0.CO;2)
- 28) de Vries, M. S., and Kroukamp, H. 2023 Decision-making skills in the fourth industrial revolution. *Teaching Public Administration*, 41(3), 389-407. <https://doi.org/10.1177/01447394221119087>
- 29) Deac, V., Vrîncuț M. and Păun, O. 2014 The Importance of Negotiation in Business Management. *Business Excellence and Management*, 4 (1), pp 37-46.
- 30) Ding, L. 2022 Improving the process of better decision-making skills in students in the society. *Global Journal of Medical, Physical and Health Education*, Vol 10 (1). DOI: 10.15651/2449-1802.22.10.042
- 31) Dodgson, M. and Gann, D. 2020 Universities Should Support More Student Entrepreneurs. Here's Why—And How. Available online: <https://www.weforum.org/agenda/2020/10/universities-should-support-more-student-entrepreneurs/> (accessed on June 02 2024).
- 32) Dwi Radianto, W.E., Efrata, T.C. and Dewi, L. 2019 Level of Financial Literacy in Young Entrepreneurs: Study on Entrepreneurship-based University. *International Conference on Economics, Education, Business and Accounting, KnE Social Sciences*, pages 385–398. DOI 10.18502/kss.v3i11.4022
- 33) Effeney, G., Carroll, A. and Bahr, N. 2013 Self-Regulated Learning: Key strategies and their sources in a sample of adolescent males. *Australian Journal of Educational & Developmental Psychology*. Vol 13, pp. 58-74. ISSN 1446-5442
- 34) Eggers, F., Lovelace, K.J. and Kraft, F. 2017 Fostering creativity through critical thinking: The case of business startup simulations. *Creativity and Innovation Management*, Vol 26 (3), p. 266-276. <https://doi.org/10.1111/caim.12225>
- 35) Farid, S. M. and Rahman, S. A. 2020 Identifying the Challenges of Involvement in Entrepreneurship Activities among a Group of Undergraduates. *International Journal of Contemporary Educational Research*, 7(2), 246-257. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.33200/ijcer.697597>
- 36) Fioravanti, M.L., de Oliveira Sestito, C. D., de Deus, W. S., Scatalon, L. P. and Barbosa, E. F. 2022 Role-Playing Games for Fostering Communication and Negotiation Skills. *IEEE Transactions on Education*, Vol. 65 (3), pp. 384-393. doi: 10.1109/TE.2021.3117898.
- 37) Gibson, C., H. Hardy III, J. and Ronald Buckley, M. 2014 Understanding the Role of Networking in Organizations. *Career Development International*, Vol. 19 No. 2, pp. 146-161. <https://doi.org/10.1108/CDI-09-2013-0111>
- 38) Gül, M., Golmohammadi, H., Pashaie, S. and Tuncer, M. 2024 Analyzing the Relationship Between Individual Time Management Skills and Business Attitude of Sports Science Students. *Physical Culture and Sport. Studies and Research*, 2024, 102, 58–69. DOI: 10.2478/pcssr-2024-0005

Entrepreneurial Skills of Student Entrepreneurs

- 39) Guliman, S.D.O. 2015 An Evaluation of Financial Literacy of Micro and Small Enterprise Owners in Iligan City: Knowledge and Skills. *Journal of Global Business*, Vol 4 (1),
- 40) Gundry, L.K., Ofstein, L.F. and Kickul, J.R. 2014 Seeing around corners: How creativity skills in entrepreneurship education influence innovation in business. *The International Journal of Management Education*, Vol 12 (3), pp 529-538. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijme.2014.03.002>
- 41) Gwija, S.A., Eresia-Eke, C. and Iwu, C.G. 2014 Challenges and Prospects of Youth Entrepreneurship Development in a Designated Community in the Western Cape, South Africa. *Journal of Economics and Behavioral Studies*, Vol. 6, No. 1, pp. 10-20. ISSN: 2220-6140.
- 42) Habaradas, R. B. and Tullao, T. S. 2017 *Pathways to Entrepreneurship*. Quezon City: Phoenix Publishing House, Inc.
- 43) Haynie, M. and Shepherd, D.A. 2009 A Measure of Adaptive Cognition for Entrepreneurship Research. *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 33: 695–714. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1540-6520.2009.00322.x>
- 44) Hidayatulloh, M.K.Y. and Ashoumi, H. 2022 Creativity and entrepreneur knowledge to increase entrepreneurial intent among vocational school students. *Journal of Education and Learning*, Vol. 16, No. 4, pp. 434~439. DOI: 10.11591/edulearn.v16i4.19771
- 45) Høgevold, N., Rodriguez, R., Svensson, G. and Otero-Neira, C. 2021 B to B Sellers' Skill Level in Sales Performance – Frameworks and Findings. *Journal of Business-to-Business Marketing*, 28(3), 265–281. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1051712X.2021.1974169>
- 46) Hung, A.A., Parker, A.M. and Yoong, J.K. 2009 Defining and Measuring Financial Literacy. RAND Working Paper Series WR-708, Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=1498674> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.1498674>
- 47) Irene, B. 2017 Women entrepreneurship in South Africa: understanding the role of competencies in business success. *The Southern Africa Journal of Entrepreneurship and Small Business Management*, Vol 9 (1). DOI:10.4102/sajesbm.v9i1.121
- 48) Jasra, J.M., Khan, M.A., Hunjra, A.I., Rehman, R.A.U. and Azam, R. 2011 Determinants of Business Success of Small and Medium Enterprises. *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, Vol. 2 No. 20. <https://ssrn.com/abstract=2130356>
- 49) Kerr, S.P., Kerr, W.R. and Xu, T. 2017 Personality Traits of Entrepreneurs: A Review of Recent Literature. (Working Paper 18-04). https://www.hbs.edu/ris/Publication%20Files/18-047_b0074a64-5428-479b-8c83-16f2a0e97eb6.pdf
- 50) Kharbanda, O.P. and Stallworthy, E.A. 1991 Negotiation: An Essential Management Skill. *Journal of Managerial Psychology*, Vol. 6 No. 4, pp. 2-52. <https://doi.org/10.1108/EUM000000001732>
- 51) Kirbaşlar, M. and Özsoy-Güneş, Z. 2015 The effect of critical thinking disposition on entrepreneurship levels: A Study on Future Teachers. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 174, 199 – 207. doi: 10.1016/j.sbspro.2015.01.647
- 52) Koe, W.L., Krishnam, R. and Utami, S. 2018 The Influence of Entrepreneurial Skills On Business Startup Intention Among Bumiputra Students. *Journal of Advanced Manufacturing Technology*, Vol. 12 (2). ISSN: 1985-3157
- 53) Kollie, J., Louw, W., Monyolo, R., Nkambule, V., Lashley, M., Oriakhi, R., Peters-Richardson, J., Tinai, S., Mphanya, T., Daniel, C. and Powley, R. 2011 Introduction to Entrepreneurship [Course Guide]. Commonwealth of Learning. <https://oasis.col.org/server/api/core/bitstreams/24fc6ce7-028e-48b7-8b48-15670a5a5223/content>
- 54) Komulainen, K., Korhonen, M. and Rätty, H. 2009 Risk-taking abilities for everyone? Finnish entrepreneurship education and the enterprising selves imagined by pupils. *Gender and Education*, 21(6), 631–649. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09540250802680032>
- 55) Kruger, M.E. 2005 Creativity in the Entrepreneurship Domain. [Doctoral Dissertation: University of Pretoria]. UPspace Institutional Repository. <http://hdl.handle.net/2263/27491>
- 56) Kurdyś-Kujawska, A. and Wojtkowska, A. 2023 To Be or Not to Be... An Entrepreneur: What Motivates and What Limits Students' Entrepreneurial Initiatives? *Scientific Papers of Silesian University of Technology Organization and Management*, Series No. 188. <http://dx.doi.org/10.29119/1641-3466.2023.188.15>
- 57) Kusmintarti, A., Thoyib, A., Maskie, G. and Ashar, K. 2016 Entrepreneurial Characteristics as a Mediation of Entrepreneurial Education Influence on Entrepreneurial Intention. *Journal of Entrepreneurship Education*, Vol 19 (1).
- 58) Lehmann, D.R. and Winer, R.S. 2005 *Product Management*, Fourth Edition. McGraw Hill Irwin: New York
- 59) Li, G., Long, Z., Jiang, Y., Huang, Y., Wang, P. and Huang, Z. 2023 Entrepreneurship education, entrepreneurship policy and entrepreneurial competence: mediating effect of entrepreneurship competition in China. *Education + Training*, Vol. 65 No. 4, pp. 607-629. <https://doi.org/10.1108/ET-06-2021-0218>
- 60) Li, Y. 2021 Research on the Growth Path of College Student Entrepreneurs—A Case Study of Chengdu City in China. *Advances in Social Science, Education and Humanities Research*, Vol 543. <https://doi.org/10.2991/assehr.k.210407.153>

Entrepreneurial Skills of Student Entrepreneurs

- 61) Lindelöf, P. and Löfsten, H. 2004 Proximity as a Resource Base for Competitive Advantage: University-Industry Links for Technology Transfer. *Journal of Technology Transfer*, 29(3-4), 311-326.
<https://doi.org/10.1023/B:JOTT.0000034125.29979.ae>
- 62) Little, B. 2018 Time Management. In: Zeigler-Hill, V., Shackelford, T. (eds) *Encyclopedia of Personality and Individual Differences*. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-28099-8_871-1
- 63) Littunen, H. 2000 Entrepreneurship and the Characteristics of the Entrepreneurial Personality. *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behavior & Research*, Vol. 6 No. 6, pp. 295-310. <https://doi.org/10.1108/13552550010362741>
- 64) Lowden, J.S. 2007 *Managerial Skills for the Entrepreneur*. Emerald Blackfiles.
- 65) Lyons, T.S. 2002 Building Social Capital for Rural Enterprise Development: Three Case Studies in the United States. *Journal of Developmental Entrepreneurship*, Vol. 7, no. 2: 193-216
- 66) Macko, A. and Tyzska, T. 2009 Entrepreneurship and Risk Taking. *Applied Psychology*, Vol 58 (3).
<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1464-0597.2009.00402.x>
- 67) Makhbul, Z.M. 2011 Entrepreneurial Success: An Exploratory Study among Entrepreneurs. *International Journal of Business and Management*, Vol. 6, No. 1; E-ISSN 1833-8119
- 68) Moore, L.L. and Rudd, R.D. 2004 Leadership Skills and Competencies for Extension Directors and Administrators. *Journal of Agricultural Education*, Vol 45 (3), pp. 22-33. DOI: 10.5032/jae.2004.03022
- 69) Oganisjana, K. and Tatjana K. 2012 Does Competence-Oriented Higher Education Lead to Students' Competitiveness? *Engineering Economics*, 23: 77–82. doi.org/10.5755/j01.ee.23.1.1228
- 70) Omeihe, I., Harrison, C., Simba, A. and Omeihe, K. 2023 The role of the entrepreneurial leader: a study of Nigerian SMEs. *International Journal of Entrepreneurship and Small Business*, Vol. 49, No. 2.
- 71) Petříková, D. and Soroková, T. 2016 Managerial and Entrepreneurial Skills as Determinants of Business. *Polish Journal of Management Studies*, Vol.14, No.1. DOI: 10.17512/pjms.2016.14.1.17
- 72) Pienaar, W.D. and Spoelstra, H.I.J. 1999 *Negotiation: Theories, Strategies and Skills*. Juta & Co, LTD.
- 73) Powers, T. L., Jennings, J. C. and DeCarlo, T. E. 2014 An assessment of needed sales management skills. *Journal of Personal Selling & Sales Management*, 34(3), 206–222. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08853134.2014.890900>
- 74) Rakib, M., Azis, M., Azis, F. and Sanusi, D.A. 2023 The Effect of Self-Leadership and Self-Efficacy on Entrepreneurship Creativity: An Empirical Study on Online Business Students. *Pegem Journal of Education and Instruction*, Vol. 13, No. 3, 209-214. DOI: 10.47750/pegegog.13.03.22
- 75) Rakib, M., Tawe, A., Azis, M., Syam, A., and Sanusi, D.A. 2022 Determinants of Entrepreneurial Intention: Empirical Study of Student Entrepreneurs. *Academic of Entrepreneurship Journal*, 26(3): 1–12.
- 76) Ratten, V. 2023 Entrepreneurship: Definitions, Opportunities, Challenges, and Future Directions. *Global Business and Organizational Excellence*, 42:79–90. DOI: 10.1002/joe.22217
- 77) Razmak, J., Pitzel, J.W., Belanger, C. and Farhan, W. 2023 Brushing up on Time-Honored Sales Skills to Excel in Tomorrow's Environment. *Journal of Business & Industrial Marketing*, Vol. 38 No. 4, pp. 701-723.
<https://doi.org/10.1108/JBIM-12-2020-0533>
- 78) Rembiasz, M. 2017 Student Entrepreneurship – Research on Development. *MATEC Web of Conferences*, 121, 12015.
DOI: 10.1051/mateconf/20171211201
- 79) Rodriguez, S. and Lieber, H. 2020 Relationship Between Entrepreneurship Education, Entrepreneurial Mindset, and Career Readiness in Secondary Students. *Journal of Experiential Education*, 43(3), 277-298.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/1053825920919462>
- 80) Romero, R.S. and Gono, E.R. 2021 Obstacles in Pursuing Business among Entrepreneurship Students. *The International Journal of Business Management and Technology*, Vol 5 (5). ISSN: 2581-3889
- 81) Russell, R., Atchison, M. and Brooks, R. 2008 Business Plan Competitions in Tertiary Institutions: Encouraging Entrepreneurship Education. *Journal of Higher Education Policy and Management*, Vol 30 (2), p123-138.
DOI: 10.1080/13600800801938739
- 82) Sandoval, L.A. 2022 The Knowledge and Skills Required to Be a Successful Entrepreneur. *Applied Economics Teaching Resources*, Vol 4 (1)
- 83) Sayari, K., Jalagat, R. and Dalluay, V. 2017 Assessing the Relationship of Time Management and Academic Performance of the Business Students in Al-Zahra College for Women. *European Business & Management*, 2017; 3(1): 1-8.
doi: 10.11648/j.ebm.20170301.11
- 84) Schimperna, F., Nappo, F. and Marsigalia, B. 2022 Student Entrepreneurship in Universities: The State-of-the-Art. *Administrative Sciences*, 12: 5. <https://doi.org/10.3390/admsci12010005>

Entrepreneurial Skills of Student Entrepreneurs

- 85) Schrum, K., and Bogdewiecz, S. 2021 Cultivating research skills through scholarly digital storytelling. *Higher Education Research & Development*, 41(7), 2382–2394. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07294360.2021.2010667>
- 86) Sen, L. 2009 *Communication Skills: Second Edition*. PHI Learning Private Limited: New Delhi
- 87) Setiawan, J.L. 2014 Examining Entrepreneurial Self-Efficacy among Students. *Procedia – Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 115, pp 235-242. doi: 10.1016/j.sbspro.2014.02.431
- 88) Shepherd, D.A. and Patzelt, H. 2017 Researching Entrepreneurial Decision Making. In: *Trailblazing in Entrepreneurship*. Palgrave Macmillan, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-48701-4_8
- 89) Siebert, J.U., Becker, M. and Oeser, N. 2022 Making a good career choice: A decision-analytical intervention to enhance proactive decision-making and career choice self-efficacy in high school students. *Decision Sciences Journal of Innovative Education*, Volume 21, Issue 1 p. 10-25. <https://doi.org/10.1111/dsji.12280>
- 90) Sousa, J.M. and Almeida, M.D.R. 2014 Entrepreneurial skills development. *Recent Advances Economics*, 135-139. ISBN: 978-960-474-394-0
- 91) Stanford University. n.d. What is Entrepreneurship? Stanford Online. <https://online.stanford.edu/what-is-entrepreneurship>
- 92) Starchenko, L. 2020 Impact of Gender Aspects of Sustainable Entrepreneurship on Country Innovative Development. *Marketing and Management of Innovations*, 4, 304-311. <http://doi.org/10.21272/mmi.2020.4-25>
- 93) Tang, C., Byrge, C. and Zhou, J. 2018 Creativity Perspective on Entrepreneurship. In: Turcan, R., Fraser, N. (eds) *The Palgrave Handbook of Multidisciplinary Perspectives on Entrepreneurship*. Palgrave Macmillan, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-91611-8_5
- 94) Tem, S., Kuroda, A. and Ngang Tang, K. 2020 The Importance of Soft Skills Development to Enhance Entrepreneurial Capacity. *International Educational Research*; Vol. 3, No. 3. <https://doi.org/10.30560/ier.v3n3p1>
- 95) Trimpop, R.M. (Ed.). 1994 Chapter 1: What Is Risk Taking Behavior?. *Advances in Psychology*. Vol 107, pp 1-14. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0166-4115\(08\)61295-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0166-4115(08)61295-9)
- 96) Twum, K.K., Kwakwa, P.A., Ofori, D. and Nkukpornu A. 2021 The Relationship Between Individual Entrepreneurial Orientation, Network Ties, and Entrepreneurial Intention of Undergraduate Students: Implications on Entrepreneurial Education. *Entrepreneurship Education*, Vol 4, 39–66. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s41959-021-00044-w>
- 97) Utama, A.N.B. and Syarif, A. 2023 Student Perspectives on Financial Literacy to Support Entrepreneurial Character. *Journal of Business Studies and Management Review*, Vol.6, No.2. E-ISSN: 2597-6265
- 98) Vicens, G.R., Casanovas, L.V., Canals, C.S. and Serra, L. 2022 Entrepreneurship Analysis in Spanish Universities. *Higher Education, Skills and Work-Based Learning*, Vol. 12 No. 1, pp. 178-190. DOI 10.1108/HESWBL-11-2020-024
- 99) Vodă, A.I., Covatariu, D. and Ghiuță, O-A. 2019 Student’s Entrepreneurial Intentions: Role of Entrepreneurial Education and Risk Taken Ability. *Environmental Engineering and Management Journal*, Vol. 18, No. 7, 1527-1534
- 100) Wait, M. and Stiehler, B. 2021 Student Self-Determination and Boundaries: An Emerging Market Perspective on the Development of Sales Skills. *South African Journal of Higher Education*, Vol. 35, No. 6. https://hdl.handle.net/10520/ejc-high_v35_n6_a14
- 101) Yener, H. 2020 Effects of Decision-Making Styles on Entrepreneurship Skills. *Technium Social Sciences Journal*, Vol 8, pp 569-578. ISSN: 2668-7798
- 102) Yohana, C. 2020 Factors Influencing the Development of Entrepreneurship Competency in Vocational High School Students: A Case Study. *International Journal of Education and Practice*, Vol. 8, No. 4, pp. 804-819. DOI: 10.18488/journal.61.2020.84.804.819
- 103) Yun, A. and McNaughton, R.B. 2021 Student Entrepreneurship at the University of Auckland 2021. *Global University Entrepreneurial Spirit Students’ Survey 2021 - National Report New Zealand*. Auckland: University of Auckland.
- 104) Yusof, M., Sandhu, M.S. and Jain, K.K. 2007 Relationship Between Psychological Characteristics and Entrepreneurial Inclination: A Case Study of Students at University Tun Abdul Razak (UNITAR). *Journal of Asia Entrepreneurship and Sustainability*, Vol III (2)
- 105) Zafar, M.J., Yasin, G., and Ijaz, M. 2012 Social networking a source developing entrepreneurial intentions among entrepreneurs: A case of Multan. *Asian Economic and Financial Review*, 2(8), 1072-1084.
- 106) Zahra, A., Fakhrisadat, N. and Narges, I. 2014 Explaining the Role of Managerial Skills of Entrepreneurship in Business Success. *International Journal of Management Sciences*, Vol. 4, No. 1, 42-52.
- 107) Ziemianski, P. and Golik, J. 2020 Including the Dark Side of Entrepreneurship in the Entrepreneurship Education. *Education Sciences*, 10, 211; doi:10.3390/educsci10080211
- 108) Zinn, J. O. 2017 The meaning of risk-taking – key concepts and dimensions. *Journal of Risk Research*, 22(1), 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13669877.2017.1351465>